

Artificial intelligence of things and distributed technologies as enablers for intelligent mobility services in smart cities-A survey

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ABSTRACT

The society is witnessing an accelerated large-scale adoption of technology with transformative effects on daily transport operations, with cities now depending on data driven mobility services. Disruptive technologies such as Artificial Intelligence (AI), the Internet of Things (IoT), and decentralized technologies for example Distributed Ledger Technologies (DLT) are being deployed in smart cities. However, AI is faced with data security and privacy issues due to its centralized mode of deployment. Conversely, DLT which employs a decentralized architecture can be converged with AI to provide a secure data sharing across various IoT thereby overcoming the existing setbacks faced in deploying AI in smart cities. Evidently, the convergence of AI and IoT as AIoT and DLT have great potential to create novel business models for improved data driven services such as intelligent mobility in smart cities. Although research on the convergence of AI, IoT and DLT exists, our understanding of its integration in achieving intelligent mobility services in smart cities remains fragmented as current research in this area remains scarce. This study bridges the gap between theory and practice by providing researchers and practitioners with insights on the potential benefits of converging AIoT and DLT. Grounded on the Technology Organization Environment (TOE) framework this study presents the technological, organizational, and environmental factors that impacts the convergence of AIoT and DLT in smart cities. Additionally, findings from this study present use cases on the applicability of AIoT and DLT to support intelligent mobility services in smart cities.

1. Introduction

A smart city is a city that deploys information and communications technologies (ICT), including Internet of Things (IoT) devices such as sensors, smart meters, etc. to help plan and manage urban infrastructure and overall improve citizens quality of life [36,56]. Smart cities employ digital technologies and interconnected systems to support critical infrastructures needed in the city such as energy, health, transportation, etc. [35,56]. Due to population increase the demand of mobility has progressively increased as well, leading to notable issues such as increasing traffic congestion and delays, collisions, and accidents mostly due to human errors (Hansain et al., 2020; [43]). Although transportations have played a focal role urban development and have proven to be a stimulus for economic growth which positively impact the sustainability of economies ([54,82]; Jnr, 2024). Researchers such as Hansain et al. (2020) advocated for studies focused in adapting urban mobility to provide an efficient, safe, effective, and sustainable mode of travel.

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The advancements in disruptive technologies, such as the Artificial intelligence (AI), IoT and Distributed Ledger Technologies (DLT) systems have transformed a broad spectrum of smart city solutions.

AI offers autonomous decision-making capabilities similar to humans, and over the years AI has rapidly progressed to executing both simple and complex tasks in different domains [22]. When AI is applied in smart cities these systems exhibit behaviors similar to human intelligence for learning, planning, reasoning, and solving problems [30,55]. Moreover, advancements in AI are also anticipated to be key enablers of future innovations in smart cities such as intelligent robots or autonomous driving, conversational agents, etc. [65]. The IoT comprises of a distributed network connecting physical devices or objects that are capable of acting on or sensing their environment and capable of communicating with each other, other machines, devices, or computer systems. IoT function and offers different kinds of intelligence and data using a variety of sensors (Hansain et al., 2020). IoT devices help to establish a digital ecosystem that enables a systematic and automated data collection, processing, sensing, analyzing, and communication processes managed, regulated, and monitored with less human intervention [2,8]. Furthermore, DLT employs a decentralize peer-to-peer approach among participants without any intermediary or a trusted third party to governs and provide secure access to a shared ledger of data and transactions. DLT is needed to manage access control for traffic management systems, travel predictions, routing, road conditions, or to secure the intelligent transport systems of autonomous cars ([65]; Jnr, 2024). DLT can be applied to address mobility related issues such as data availability, ownership, access and sharing in the transportation sector today has continue to be hindered due to different standards, unclear regulatory policies, the lack of data usage control, among others. Also, DLT can be utilized to provide smarter mobility solutions such as real-time traffic management, traffic routing and navigation, on-demand mobility, seamless intermodal trips, first and last mile, intelligent personal travel assistant, etc. (Jnr, 2024)

Findings from the literature suggest that the deployment of AI and DLT has transformed supply chains by digitizing manual-based processes, facilitating trustworthy data sharing, and enabling autonomous transactions ([51,40]). Moreover, the convergence of AI and DLT can revolutionize smart city infrastructures to achieve sustainable ecosystems for IoT systems. AI helps to analyze and generate insights from data produced from IoT to provide interpretation that improves intelligent mobility services by detecting patterns and optimizing urban mobility. Hence, to analyzes data produced from IoT, AI can be used to derived descriptive, prescriptive, and predicted inference to delivers scalable and efficient data driven mobility services in smart cities [8]. Thus, the confluence of AI and IoT as AIoT, and DLT can be a key accelerator for enabling digitalization of cities into smarter and more sustainable cities. The integration of AIoT and DLT provide opportunities for supporting cities to develop smarter and sustainable infrastructures. Moreover, the deployment of AIoT and DLT can improve intelligent mobility services by facilitating seamlessly connection of heterogeneous devices, sensors, or and metering devices installed on public transport infrastructures. Accordingly, AI, IoT, and DLT can be leveraged to provide intelligent mobility solutions in smart cities for providing a safer, connected, and sustainable mode of travel for citizens (Hansain et al., 2020).

But until recently, researchers only separately studied AI, IoT, and DLT applications in smart cities, focusing on their specific application. Prior studies mostly explored the application of AI, DLT, and IoT in isolation. Although few studies such as Salah et al. [70] discussed the integration of AI and DLT and the significance of such integration in the society. Studies that explored potential synergies of AIoT and DLT in smart cities is still in its infancy [42]. Also, to date, there is lack of comprehensive studies that review the role of AIoT and DLT in improving mobility services in smart cities. While in practice the convergence of AIoT and DLT improves processes for seamlessness and greater efficiency to generate new value creation potentials for cities, there are limited knowledge on the factors that influence the convergence of these technologies. AI systems generally process large amounts of data for versatile and better decision making. Likewise, AIoT systems are faced with data security, data leaks, misuse of personal data and privacy issue as they are mostly based on a centralized architectures where a single point of failure usually compromises the entire system ([27,51,40]). Thus, AIoT infrastructure employs centralized data storage using cloud-based data centers, which has become a major setback for developing privacy preserving and highly secure applications [70]. Thus, this paper aims to examine the following research questions.

- What is the current state-of-the-art on the technological convergence of AIoT and DLT in smart cities?
- What are the technological, organizational, and environmental factors that impacts the convergence of AIoT and DLT in smart cities?
- How can the convergence of AIoT and DLT support the actualization of intelligent mobility services in smart cities?

Therefore, this study aims to investigate how the deployment of disruptive technologies such as AIoT and DLT can support intelligent mobility services for passengers and drivers in smart cities. Accordingly, a systematic review and meta-analysis was adopted, and the Technology Organization Environment (TOE) framework was adopted in this study to present the technological, organizational, and environmental factors that impacts the convergence of AIoT and DLT in smart cities. Evidence from this study present uses cases showing the feasible application of AIoT and DLT to support intelligent mobility services in smart cities. The remaining part of this article is structured as follows. [Section 2](#) is literature review. [Section 3](#) is the research methodology. [Section 4](#) is the findings. [Section 5](#) is the discussions and implications, and [Section 6](#) is the conclusion.

2. Literature review

2.1. DLT for intelligent mobility services in smart cities

A ledger is a file that records, tracks, and logs the ownership and access of assets. A distributed ledger provides a shared database via a decentralized network members which updated based on a consensus algorithm employed to record transactions. It uses a unique

cryptographic signature which offers a tamper-proof auditable timestamped provenance of all transactions [76]. Distributed Ledger Technology (DLT) is a new form of a decentralized database that guarantees the integrity of data transactions [29]. DLT is an infrastructure which enables information to be recorded, and jointly managed in distributed manner by different users across a peer-to-peer network, unlike the conventional medium of storing data within a central server [47]. DLT offers a distributed and structured network of nodes that cryptographically share secure data within a public verifiable ledger [22]. DLT has continued to emerge as a disruptive innovation that will transform the way enterprises cooperate, automate billing, trace, and track transactions. DLT are known as immutable virtual ledgers duplicated and dispersed across different computer networks [60]. DLT is one of the most hyped technologies and has been gaining a lot of attention as a technology to be widely adopted across domains. Since 2008 with the contribution of Satoshi Nakamoto's Bitcoin whitepaper [61]. DLT offers a cross party and multi-stakeholder systems that process data using a decentralized manner in trustless environments [8].

Currently, the applications of DLT in smart cities such as blockchain goes beyond enabling financial transactions to the management of decentralized infrastructures, autonomous vehicles, medical data, tracking and tracing source of energy, etc. [8,65]. Due to its distributed feature and tamper-proof nature, DLT can be applied in to address data access, security, and improving privacy to support intelligent mobility services [2,41]. DLT can allow safe distribution and secure storage of data across different mobility mode of travel [2]. DLT can be cost effective in limiting the need for a centralized permission to govern and verify transactions and interactions among mobility service providers and commuters [24]. Therefore, DLT have recently gained much attention in intelligent mobility services as an infrastructure for addressing the ambivalence of data generated from different public transport modes.

DLT supports the mobility operation via an appendonly database (i.e., the distributed ledger). DLT can be employed to provide irrefutable proof that a set of transactions or process occurred between parties during shared ride or carpooling [27]. DLT helps to establish trust in ride sharing services without the need of a third-party ([29]; Jnr, 2024). As the main features of DLT comprises of decentralization immutability, transparency, auditability, autonomy, attacks resilient, security, data integrity, and anonymity [32]. DLT offers new opportunities to smart cities to deploy decentralized intelligent mobility architecture with the same level of assurance, without a need of a trusted third parties or centralized architectures to verify data or transactions. Hence, DLT has the potential to enable smart mobility services by improving trust, enhancing security, and promoting decentralized intelligence [32].

2.2. AI for intelligent mobility solution in smart cities

Artificial intelligence (AI) is another prominent technology first presented in the artificial neuron model (McCulloch and Pitts, 1943) and the 1950 academic paper focused on Computing Machinery and Intelligence (Turing, 1950; [78]), enables machines to have cognitive capabilities for learning, making inference, and adapting based on data it collects [70]. AI refers to an autonomous machine that can analyze and process information in an intelligent way, often analogous to the way human beings perform similar tasks [56]. AI can also be referred to as machines that are programmed to execute different operations such as identifying, learning, and solving routinely several problems [72]. AI comprises of a large continuum of machine intelligence from text to speech to driverless and autonomous vehicles [27]. AI offers the capability of computer systems to not only make decisions that were formerly made by only humans. AI is also able to make decisions from large volume of data from complex or uncertain environments. The domain of AI started in the mid 1950's and of recent it has seen a much interest due to digitalization and the growing amounts of data in the society [43], to build computer systems that can simulate human intelligence [3]. Researchers such as Gupta et al. [34] stated that AI possess the ability to identify patterns to make critical decisions that are mostly challenging for humans.

AI can provide autonomous processing and analysis of large data sets for decision making support. AI is able to embed intelligence in physical devices, sensors system, and thus can be integrated with IoT devices to enable physical infrastructure to automatically cope in different environments. Today, AI is being applied in the society in businesses, home appliances, cars, buildings, smart phones, by mobility service operator to provide the most effective routes for commuters to arrive to their desired locations [27]. AI is evidently playing a key role in providing prescriptive and predictive analysis as recommendations for decision making support [16]. In smart cities AI offers intellectual and customized decision-making for humans in different domain areas and of application use cases. To address societal challenges faced in smart cities, AI systems can simulate human intelligence for learning, planning, predicting, prescribing, and describing problem solving alternatives [66]. AI systems mostly deploy a centralization architecture to process large volume of data set at its core with evolving and continuous stages of regularization, training model creation, and optimization [66].

2.3. IoT for data enabled mobility services in smart cities

IoT comprises of a connected network of physical devices or objects that are able to sense, communicate, or interact with either their internal states or their external environment [75]. IoT is associated with sensor-based infrastructures which relevance has increased due to massive volume of data generated in real-time from physical devices deployed in smart cities. In smart city environment IoT comprises of machines, actuators, moving objects, smart devices, and sensors that provides real-time connectivity for urban applications [2]. The integrating of digital information and different devices into real world scenarios has been achieved by the IoT. As such the IoT is a fast-emerging field, with an estimation of billion devices. The "things" in IoT refers to physical devices, such as sensors, meters, actuators, equipment, facilities, machines, vehicles, etc., connected to the Internet via inter-device communications. The things are connected to sensors to sense and perceive the deployed environment and execute a communication with other connected things. Hence, the things sense data to perform any predefined action by monitoring the deployed environment. IoT is enabled by embedded sensors that facilitate real-time collection of application related data [60].

Using IoT smart cities can collect data, push, and share collected data across a network of connected devices (Hansain et al., 2020).

To improve intelligent mobility data produced from IoT devices can be processed and analyzed to provide insights and suggest measures for cost savings, increase effectiveness or improve mobility related services provided to citizens (Hansain et al., 2020; Jnr, 2024). Citizens can access the devices via the Internet and are informed by the carrying out of functions within the IoT, and consequently, users can take action in controlling their environment. Accordingly, IoT are able to operate across heterogeneous environments and enable rich management, analyses, and control of complex interactions [33]. The IoT can provide a network-based environment for sharing of data, handling of data resources and storage, etc., can be done efficiently and quickly [25].

With the rapid digitalization of cities into smart cities the adoption of physical devices is expected to be reach 500 billion in the year 2030 [75]. In smart cities devices or sensors can generate and share large volumes of data in real-time to achieve connected systems [75]. Moreover, in smart cities different devices are connected together via the Internet which enables them to collectively execute different functions to facilitate data enabled mobility services [9]. The IoT can boost the digitalization, enhance the efficiency of the existing architectures and processing mechanisms of cities infrastructure such as in education, healthcare, public transportation, and so on [25,33]. Presently since most IoT systems are based on a centralized approach [56], it is challenging to sufficiently achieve a scalable and flexible architecture that meet the progressively complex demands required in smart city environment.

3. Research methodology

A Systematic Literature Review (SLR) was adopted in this study as the methodological approach. A SLR offers a structured, explicit, and rigorous process to identify, assess, and synthesize existing knowledge to examine a specific research question [48,49,69]. For researchers to carry out a SLR, a well-defined strategy is required. Accordingly, this study adopted the four steps proposed in the literature [16,48,49,69,84], to carry out a SLR as shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1 depicts the strategy employed to carry out the SLR based on 4 key stages which are further described below.

3.1. Framing the problem

This involves identifying the purpose of the review and formulating of possible research question(s) [49,84]. In this study the main research questions are presented in the introduction section of this article.

3.2. Selection for inclusion

This phase involves the data collection procedure employed for identifying sources and evaluating their suitability to answer the research question(s) being examined in the study [48,69]. To accomplish this, a set of selection criteria were used for including or excluding sources. For any source to be included in this systematic review, the source had to:

- Be a journal article, conference paper, technical reports, book, or chapter published between the years 1990 and 2024 to be inclusive. This study opted to select sources from 1990 as a starting year analogous to prior study [69], as based on observation from the literature the smart city concept begun to evolve around that period.
- Thesis reports, web links, and unpublished works were excluded.
- Mainly focused on technological convergence of AI, IoT, and DLTs such as blockchain in smart cities or other contexts.
- Must be grounded on a theoretical, conceptual, or empirical paper; and
- Definitely be published in English language.
- Discussed the technological, organizational, and environmental factors that influence the convergence of AIoT and DLT in smart cities.

Sources that did not correspond to these criteria, for instance, by examining other disruptive technologies (e.g. digital twin, virtual reality, augmented reality, etc.), in smart cities context were excluded. Also, studies that did not fully converge either AI, IoT, DLT, and

Fig. 1. Systematic literature review strategy employed.

big data were excluded.

3.3. Searching the literature

In searching for suitable sources, a search strategy was employed to help discover and identify key information sources [49]. In this study a search strategy based on different steps was followed. In the first step, a computerized search was carried out using multiple keywords. The selected keywords relate to the research questions being investigated in this study. Table 1 highlights the keywords used in carrying the search query from different online database.

The selected online databases comprised of Web of science, ScienceDirect, Scopus, and Google Scholar. Using these online databases as suggested by Anthony Jr [8]; Rjab et al. [69] this study carried out a backward and forward search of relevant literature in August 2022 and then in January 2024. Fig. 2 shows the selection process carried out to select sources based on the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analysis (PRISMA) as employed by prior review studies [8,9]. Based on the initial searched sources (as shown in from Fig. 2), 297 potential sources were retrieved from the specified online databases using the keywords specified in Table 1. 26 sources were found as duplicates and were excluded. This resulted to 271 sources which titles and abstract were assessed to check if the sources discuss on issues related to technology convergence of any of these two disruptive technologies (AI, IoT, and DLT).

Then 84 sources were deleted as the titles and abstract were not linked to the study area leading to 187 sources qualified for full-text assessment. After scanning through the sources in relation to the research questions being examined in this study no papers were excluded. The selected 187 sources were then checked with the inclusion and exclusion (as previously described). Thus, 100 sources were removed as they did not meet the inclusion criteria. This resulted to 82 sources. In addition, 5 studies providing guide on how to write a systematic literature review was included [16,48,49,69,84]. The final list of sources included are presented in the reference section of this paper.

3.4. Extracting, synthesizing, and analyzing data

The extraction and syntheses of data is an important step in any SLR procedure. This is because in this phase data is collected from the identified sources (see Fig. 2), as information that can help to answer the specified research question(s) [69]. Accordingly, data related the year of publication, disruptive technologies employed, research methodology employed, country of published authors, and context investigated are extracted from each source. The information extracted and synthesized from this study was stored in a Microsoft Excel sheet. Furthermore, findings as answers to the research questions are presented through an in-extensive analysis and a thorough reading of all the sources selected. Following primary data extraction, and coding of the data was carried out manually to ensure accuracy and reliability of the data analysis as seen in Section 4.2. The synthesized data as related to the research questions are presented in Section 4.2. Overall, the data was thematized and analyzed using descriptive analysis.

4. Findings

4.1. General characteristics of the selected sources

The distribution of the sources published per year (Fig. 3) suggest that research related to technology convergence of disruptive technologies (AI, IoT, DLT, and big data), has increased over the years as seen in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3 depicts the number of sources included in this study starting from 1990 to 2024. The result shows a very limited number of articles published from 1990 to 2012. The result further suggests that the rate of published sources on technology convergence of AI, IoT, DLT, and big data in different domain s such as in smart cities has increased to an average about five articles per year for the period 2018 to 2024. This publication trend reinforces that the interest of AI, IoT, DLT, and big data in different research domains has grown over recent years. This awareness and adoption of these disruptive technologies can be explained by the attractiveness of these technologies generally for the society. Although there is a drop in 2022 and 2024, a potential reason is due to the issues faced in adopting these disruptive technologies in smart cities as shown in Fig. 9.

Table 1

Deployed search string.

RQs	Search string
1	((“Artificial Intelligence” OR “Machine Learning” OR “AI” OR “Machine Learning Algorithm” OR “Machine Learning Models”) AND (“Internet of Things” OR “IoT” OR “Devices” OR “Sensors” OR “Physical Infrastructure *AND (“Distributed Ledger Technologies” OR “Distributed Ledger ” OR “DLT” OR “Blockchain”) AND (“Convergence” OR “Integration” OR “Amalgamation”) AND (“Smart Cit” OR “Sustainable Cit” OR “Digital Cit” OR “Future Cit” OR “Intelligent Cit”))
2	((“Artificial Intelligence” OR “Machine Learning” OR “Distributed Ledger Technologies” OR “Blockchain” OR “Internet of Things”) AND (“Technological ” OR “Organizational ” OR “Environmental ”) AND (“Usage ” OR “Acceptance ” OR “Deployment ” OR “Implementation ” OR “Adoption ”) AND (“Model ” OR “Framework ” OR “Approach ” OR “Architecture ”))
3	((“Artificial Intelligence” OR “Machine Learning” OR “Distributed Ledger Technologies” OR “Blockchain” OR “Internet of Things”) AND (“Smart Mobility” OR “Intelligent Mobility ” OR “Shared Mobility ” OR “Collaborative Mobility ” OR “ Collected Mobility ”) AND (“Electric Mobility” OR “Carpooling ” OR “Car Sharing ” OR “Electric Car Sharing ” OR “Car Rental ”))

Fig. 2. Sources selection process presented carried out using PRISMA flow diagram.

Fig. 3. Number of sources included from 1990 to 2024.

Findings from Fig. 4 highlight the types of disruptive technologies employed by the selected sources included in this study. Among the results, Fig. 4 suggest that 22 studies employed AI and BC in different domain, whereas 14 studies employed other disruptive technologies. Also, 9 sources adopted DLT, whereas 9 sources employed IoT, AI, and BC, and 6 sources employed big data technologies. However, there are fewer studies that employed AI, IoT, and DLT are reported in the literature. This suggests a need for research in employing these disruptive technologies in the society.

Fig. 5 depicts the research methodology employed in the sources included in this study. Overall, this result suggests that literature review was the most employed research methodology following the studies that employed simulations and experiments. Then it is survey-based studies and those that employed experiments. In summary literature review was the mostly employed research

Fig. 4. Number of sources by type of disruptive technologies employed.

methodology in the area of technology convergence across different research areas. This is based on the fact that technology convergence is still an emerging area. Therefore, there is need for more evidence and practice-based studies that provide real life experience on the capabilities of technology convergence of AI, IoT, and DLT in smart cities and the society as large.

Findings from Fig. 6 shows the distribution of all the countries of the selected sources included in this study. The result suggest that the published sources included a total of 34 countries. Most of the published sources are located in Norway, USA, India, Australia, UK, China, Canada, Germany and Pakistan. In summary the results reveal that the sources were published in Europe, North America, Asia, and Africa. Also, a qualitative report of the data sources for domains and respective countries of authors institutions are summarized in the Appendix.

Evidence from Fig. 7 shows the domain explored by the selected sources. The findings suggest that most of the sources are employed technology convergence of disruptive technologies are in smart cities domain. Additionally, the result suggest that most studies employed these disruptive technologies in organizational context, general context, healthcare, virtual enterprise, in general technology convergence and 6G/5G communications as compared to other areas. But, studies that employed AI, IoT, and DLT in mobility sectors are limited. As such there is need for studies that can address this gap in knowledge.

4.2. Role of technology convergence in smart cities

4.2.1. Technology convergence of IoT and DLT in smart cities

Smart cities integrate objects referred to as Things, equipped with actuating, sensing, and networking capabilities with dynamic control and monitoring services [39,60]. The IoT is the latest technology evolving to connect heterogeneous devices for

Fig. 5. Distribution of research methodology adopted.

Fig. 6. Distribution of published countries of selected sources.

communication. IoT devices are pervasive for example, IoT devices such as sensors and smart meters collect data from the deployed environment and can be used to autonomously interact with smart locks used in electric mobility assets, self-driving vehicles, etc. Sensors, video cameras or other devices could also be used to verify users of mobility assets installed in smart cities [56]. But the deployment of IoT in smart cities is faced with challenges such as secure data access, trustworthy data, ensuring privacy-preserving methods. Accordingly, DLT can be integrated with IoT to enable consensus on data sharing to ensure trust, privacy, and security among the city infrastructures. DLT can be employed decentralized, immutable ledger to offer trusted, auditable data. Moreover, DLT can be employed to authenticate IoT devices in smart cities and can also increase trust by enforcing identity management of IoT devices. DLT deploys smart contracts which can be used to automate processes and transactions, ensuring confidence and trust between the physical and digital infrastructure [56]. DLT enable identity management of assets by registering mobility assets with individual digital identities.

Identity management via DLT for intelligent mobility ensures that transactions or data sharing mobility assets receives a digital identity within the distributed ledger based on their physical identity (e.g., identity number for users and enterprise register). Based on these identity management, transactions can be processed autonomously between users, enterprises for instance a car sharing company. This can also be extended to transactions between individuals and machines (e.g., traveler and an autonomous car) or among two machines (for example: payment transfer from electric car and charging station (Anthony [40]), with low transaction costs and fast transaction speed [56]. Additionally, in the application context, DLT can be deployed with IoT to facilitate intelligent machine-to-machine communication. As DLT employs smart contracts that can allow machines such as electric vehicles to receive payment (e.g., for electric car rental), and make payment (e.g., for parking, charging, toll, etc.), using tokens or cryptocurrencies to carry out transactions and make decisions based on the existing business logic (Jnr, 2024). Such capability provided by DLT can help to remotely manage IoT devices while safeguarding a trusted connection between IoT devices [56].

By integrating DLT with IoT trusted peer-to-peer data sharing can be facilitated between devices, supporting machine-to-machine transactions and communications. This could lessen data bottlenecks and reduce vendor lock-in associated with centralized systems and also give sovereignty to stakeholders in managing ownership and controls of their data [56]. DLT could be used to secure the provenance for data generated from IoT devices as an audit trail to assist with monitoring the state of the device used for intelligent mobility services. Similarly, DLT can help provide a trusted, common communications interface across different types of IoT devices supporting interoperability. DLT can also help reinforce the IoT network, by offering decentralized device logs. Furthermore, in the

Fig. 7. Distribution of domains explored by selected sources.

infrastructure context, IoT devices for instance iris scanners and fingerprint, face recognition devices, QR codes, built-in sensors, GPS trackers, etc., are often used to authentication for identity information in the physical world. After identifications have been created, DLT can be used to secure a tamper-proof connection between IoT devices and their data source [56].

The integration of IoT and DLT can support smart city services by providing interface for devices and sensors to interact and perform economic transactions for providing intelligent mobility services without the involvement of third parties via Peer-to-Peer (P2P) for DLT and Machine-to-Machine (M2M) for IoT. Compared to a centralized IoT architecture, blockchain offers distributed data loads with all IoT devices contributing to data integrity using public key infrastructure and majority consensus before data transactions are permitted. Options for IoT blockchain include: Ethereum, deploying smart contracts permanently kept on the blockchain and executed upon users' requests. Hyperledger, applying access control, chain code-based smart contracts, and variable consensus methods [60]. According to a report by the international data corporation up to 10 percent of pilot and deployment blockchain will incorporate some sort of IoT sensors. As DLT can offer a decentralized storage to immutably store data generated by IoT devices enabling autonomous control of smart devices without any central controller. By implementing DLT, connected IoT devices can be tracked, microtransactions can be processed, and several devices can be coordinate to significantly decrease operational cost. Overall, DLT makes IoT devices to be more secure, trustworthy, and resilient [75], by migrating from centralized architectures to distributed and decentralized P2P network, thereby ensuring higher resilience to cyber-attacks [60].

4.2.2. Technology convergence of AI and DLT in smart cities

AI is able to embed intelligence in mobility infrastructures by integrating IoT devices to autonomously cope with different urban environments [25]. DLT can contribute by improving operational decentralization thereby keeping permanent footprints of interactions between data, systems, and users. Also, DLT can facilitate secure and traceable information transfer among diverse stakeholders involved in providing intelligent mobility services [70]. However, findings from the literature discussed that the integration of AI and DLT is scarce [65]. Specifically, prior research lacks an understanding on how AI and DLT can support each other and how these technologies can be mutually integrated to support intelligent mobility in today's society. However, achieving privacy-aware and high-accurate data driven intelligent mobility systems enabled by Machine Learning (ML) a subset of AI is still challenging in smart cities. With the use of DLT it becomes possible for address the trustworthiness faced by AI based systems. As DLT checks, verifies, and stores every transaction or data cryptographically using hash functions within the distributed networks enabling provenance on training models and data which significantly improves the trustworthiness of these models and data [75].

DLT can empower AI especially ML for supporting data and model sharing, improving privacy and security, and also fostering decentralized intelligence for trusted decision-making support. DLT based system can store data in a tamper-resistant and secure manner to ensure data auditability and confidentiality using cryptographic techniques. Specifically, DLTs such as blockchain can enable a decentralized access control without relying in any central entities. Likewise, Federated Learning (FL), which is a method deployed to train AI/ML models via distributed paradigms while preserving user privacy can also be employed to improve data security as mentioned in the literature [85], where FL was proposed to train disaster detection frameworks in smart cities. Similarly, findings from [6] proposed integrating blockchain with FL to further enhance the privacy of AIoT systems. Therefore, leveraging DLT, ML could train, learn, and securely derive decisions on local devices in distributed and decentralized networks. Additionally, DLT can enable the transparent auditing of the training data employed by ML algorithms to be reviewed any time by authorized node users with secure access to the system [75]. On the other hand, AI can support DLT for efficiency energy consumption, improve scalability, and autonomy of smart contracts deployed by DLT.

Thus, ML algorithms provide a feasible solution to create and deploy complicated smart contracts making them more effective. ML algorithms can predict and provide a feasible data driven method for processing transactions within the distributed ledger. In addition, the integration of DLT and ML may revolutionize the mobility sector in smart cities to make it become much smarter and more efficient. DLT gives the control of data back into users [30], enabling data sovereignty, governance, and access, thus aiding users to have more trust and control in sharing data and knowing that their data will be used properly by AI to provide personalized mobility services (Anthony [40]c). Leveraging ML algorithms, DLT systems can support predictive analytics ensuring the requirements for intelligent mobility operations. ML can address scalability issues faced in DLT by optimizing data storage and maintenance by offering a much efficient data pruning or sharding solutions [75]. AI can enhance the efficiency of DLT by decreasing the processing power required to perform computational tasks. AI can help in simplification and optimization of DLT to reduce errors and improve the performance and adaptability of DLT [60].

In smart cities data is produced from several sources and some of these data are provided from untrusted third-party, DLT provides immutability and traceability of data in a distributed approach. This will encourage citizens to trust AI's fairness, accuracy, and transparency [60]. Moreover, DLT guarantees credibility and integrity of data stored in the distributed ledgers, and AI can help in data analysis and improve the intelligence of smart contracts deployed by DLT resulting to intelligent mobility applications in smart cities (Jnr, 2024). AI can efficiently detect malicious behavior within the decentralized network by deploying trained ML algorithms and models. In this way, AI could assist DLT in identifying and reducing fraud and illegal transactions [75]. Moreover, the transparent auditability and accountability features of DLT can support the trustworthiness of data and ML models thereby providing a traceable ML process. DLT is presently faced with some challenges such as the interoperability of different DLT [8]. Specifically, using training data, ML algorithms may provide a viable way to operate different DLT and optimize data storage and maintenance for DLT based system. ML algorithms may manage consensus mechanisms or protocols such as Proof of Work (PoW), Proof of Stake (PoS), etc. in a more intelligent manner [75].

4.3. Comparative review and landscape on integration of AI, IoT, and DLT

Evidence from the literature reveals that a few studies have investigated the integration of AI, IoT, DLT, and Big Data (BD) across different landscape and domains as shown in Table 2.

Findings from Table 2 reviewed 38 studies that integrated AI, IoT, DLT such as BC, big data, cloud computing, and edge computing in different domains highlighting the landscape of existing works. Evidence from the reviewed studies reveal that although studies such as Abraham et al. [1] explored smart toll application by employing IoT, AI and BC. Also, Karlson'Charlie' Hargroves and Stantic [43] investigated the potential for AI and BC to support the transport sector and lastly Ahmed et al. [2] presented a BC and AI enabled smart IoT framework for sustainable city. There are fewer studies that examined the convergence of AIoT and DLT to provide intelligent mobility services in smart cities. Hence this study adds to the body of knowledge by addressing this gap in knowledge.

4.4. Significance of AIoT-based DLT for intelligent mobility services in smart cities

Smart cities utilize data provided from different sources to provide value added services to citizens and other stakeholders [9]. To effectively manage digital services provided to meet the changing needs and requirements of citizens there is need to employ novel technologies. Accordingly, AI, IoT and DLT can be adopted to improve public transport by providing intelligent mobility services in smart cities. AI, IoT, and DLT are one of key disruptive technologies driving digital transformation of cities into smarter and more sustainable cities [10]. Findings from the literature further stated that the convergence of AI, IoT, and DLT have the potential to disrupt and improve current urban processes by creating sustainable business models. Based on the literature [22,30,59,70], Fig. 8 depicts the synergic to be derived from both AIoT and DLT highlighting how technology can support each other.

In smart cities IoT devices collect and provides real time data, whereas DLT can support digital infrastructure that provide intelligent mobility services, while AI can optimize the data driven processes and procedures. In urban context, these three technologies are complementary and can be exploited to achieve their full potential if integrated [71], for example in emergence and disaster detection [67,73], etc. Additionally, DLT's decentralized and immutable capabilities aid explainable AI decisions for citizens and stakeholders. AI helps to analyze user mobility requests, recognize patterns, and forecast users' needs and demand using available data thereby providing a personalized mobility experience for users [65]. Evidence from the literature [71] argued that the convergence of these technologies can support the deployment of autonomous business models such as innovative decentralized intelligence for smart mobility services in smart cities. According to a 2018 report published by the McKinsey Global Institute, it was projected that

Table 2
Comparative review of studies that integrated AI, IoT, and DLT.

Author(s), year, and contributions	Technology convergence	Explored areas	Methodology employed	Context	Business model	Countries
Aman et al. [7] investigated residential BC and IoT based energy systems.	IoT + BC	Energy storage	Literature review	Presents hurdles that IoT and BC must overcome to move beyond hype to mainstream acceptance.	Energy and IoT model.	Malaysia
Bibri et al. [23] studied on achieving smarter eco-cities.	IoT + AI	Smart cities	Literature review	Discussed employing AIoT solutions for environmental sustainability.	AI/AIoT-driven system for smart eco-cities.	Switzerland and Norway
Dong and Feng [31] designed a wireless temperature measurement network system.	AI + BC	Electrical power engineering	Experiments	Discussed the technical standards for smart grid communication and IoT equipment monitoring.	IoT-based wireless measurement of energy.	China
Nayomi et al. [62] designed a cloud-based framework to countermeasure phishing attacks.	AI + ML + BC	Smart cities	Experiments	Employ technologies to detect and prevent phishing attacks.	Cloud assisted framework for phishing detection.	India
Nguyen et al. [64] presented the essential roles of IoT and AI in smart cities.	IoT + AI	Smart cities	Literature review	Presented the components of the IoT-based smart city.	Technology-based IoT architectural model.	Canada
Alaeddini et al. [4] researched on the convergence of AI and BC in smart cities.	AI + BC	Smart cities	Literature review	Identified research hotspots, key insights, emerging trends, and specialties, in smart cities.	AI-BC architectural model.	France
Alahi et al. [5] explored the integration of IoT and AI for smart city scenario.	IoT + AI	Smart cities	Literature review	Discussed opportunities presented by integrating IoT and AI in smart cities to enhance the quality of life of citizens.	IoT-enabled architectural model.	Thailand, Germany, and Australia
Bothra et al. [25] investigated the applications of BC and AI to improve performance of IoT.	AI + BC	Computer networks	Literature review	Discussed how both BC and AI can be employed with the IoT to design robust and automated secure IoT model.	AI based BC and IoT-enabled ecosystems.	India
Khan et al. [45] examined the use of AI and BC for secure smart grid and power distribution.	AI + BC	Power distribution	Literature review	Designed a framework to maintain an operational universal defense hierarchy in real-time.	Pseudo-smart contracts and digital signatures model.	Pakistan, China, India, and Lebanon
Li et al. [53] presented applications and methods for smart energy management.	AI+ BD+ IoT+ BC	Energy management	Literature review	Discussed on an efficient and seamless integration of technologies in the energy domain to a low-carbon system.	Smart energy management model.	Canada, Turkey
Tyagi et al. [79] researched on BC-IoT applications in industry and society.	IoT + BC	Industry 5.0 and Society 5.0	Literature review	Offered a real-time view of BC-IoT based applications.	AI-BC architectural model.	India
Ullah et al. [80] investigated the role of IoT and ML in a data-centric smart environment.	IoT + ML	Smart cities	Literature review	Discuss the issues faced with deploying IoT and ML in urban environments	IoT and ML based model.	China, Pakistan, USA, Saudi Arabia
Ahmed et al. [2] developed a BC and AI enabled smart IoT framework for sustainable city.	IoT + AI + BC	Sustainable city	Literature review	Introduced a conceptual framework to process and obtain necessary information.	Layer-based architecture.	Pakistan, China, Korea, and Iran
Bellagarda and Abu-Mahfouz [22] described the integration of DLT and AI.	AI + DLT	Technology convergence	Literature review	Discussed research gaps and identified possible open research challenges.	Distributed-ledger-based AI applications.	South Africa

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Table 2 (continued)

Author(s), year, and contributions	Technology convergence	Explored areas	Methodology employed	Context	Business model	Countries
Kumar et al. [51] characterized the usefulness of AI and BC across businesses.	AI + BC	Business	Literature review	Presented different application fields in business that can gain from AI and BC.	AI-BC integration in business.	India, Malaysia, Australia, and UK
Muhati et al. [60] explored how to secure technologies from persistent cyber threats.	IoT + AI + BC + EC	Cyber safety	Literature review	Defined prospects for addressing cybersecurity concerns.	Cyber security model.	USA
Rawlins and Jagannathan [68] designed an intelligent DLT construction algorithm for IoT.	IoT + ML + DLT	Efficiency and security	Simulations and experiments	Proposed a ML approach that resolved efficiency and security issues on limited devices.	Intelligent ledger construction general threat model	USA
Ajlouni et al. [3] conducted a survey of AI based BC.	AI + BC	Blockchain Intelligence	Literature review	Discussed on the collaboration of AI and BC.	BC Intelligence model.	Turkey
Chiu and Lim [26] explored how AI and DLT can transform corporate governance.	AI + DLT	Governance and business	Literature review	Assess the technological change impacts of AI and DLT in institutions.	AI and DLT governance model.	UK and Singapore
Hu et al. [37] designed a dynamic resource sharing (DRS) architecture for 6G	AI + BC	6G	Simulations and experiments	Aimed to improve distribution, security, automation, pattern recognition & decision-making in DRS.	AI-empowered DRS architecture.	Singapore, China
Karlson'Charlie'Hargroves and Stantic [43] investigated the potential for AI and BC to aid the transport sector.	AI + BC	Transport sector	Literature review	Presented a set of industry partner-preferred use cases for transport agencies.	Real-time pay-as-you-drive model.	Australia
Miglani and Kumar [59] presented a taxonomy for BC and ML in an IoT domain.	IoT + ML + BC	5 G and B5 G technologies	Literature review	Provided guide for future use cases of these emerging technologies in 5 G and B5 G technologies.	BC and ML for 5 G and B5 G IoT applications.	India, Taiwan, and Saudi Arabia
Sharma et al. [72] designed a BC-based IoT architecture with AI.	AI + BC	IoT applications	Simulations and experiments	Aimed to achieve a secure intelligent blockchain framework.	AI-BC architectural model.	Russia
Abraham et al. [1] designed a collaborative intelligence approach for smart toll application.	IoT + AI + BC	Smart toll	Simulations and experiments	Presented a possible solution to enable real-time smart contracts between the cars and tolls.	AI-enabled multi-agent systems.	India
Dietzmann et al. [29] researched on use of DLT and AI for end-to-end reference lending.	AI + DLT	Financial services	Semi-structured interviews	Presented principles for the design and development of future DLT-based AI applications.	Distributed-ledger-based AI applications.	Germany and Switzerland
Karger [42] provided a review of the emerging field of AI and BC.	AI + BC	Companies	Literature review	Provided a categorization of the different alternatives for connecting AI and BC.	AI-BC architecture.	Germany
Kim and Park [46] designed a BC-based data-preserving AI based learning environment model.	IoT + AI + BC	Cyber security	Literature review	Aimed to employ AI to improve cybersecurity in IoT environments.	BC-based AI learning data open network.	Korea
Sandner et al. [71] explored the convergence of AI, IoT, BC for autonomous business models.	IoT + AI + BC	Industrial corporations	Literature review	Proposed that the convergence of AI, IoT, BC can support digital transformation.	Autonomous agent based digital twin/IoT.	Germany
Singh et al. [74] presented a BC-based intelligent IoT architecture with AI.	IoT + AI + BC	Cloud and edge computing (EC)	Literature review	Aimed to support an efficient big data analysis.	BC-enabled intelligent IoT architecture	Korea
Pandl et al. [65] showed the feasibility of using the convergence concept for AI and DLT.	AI + DLT	Technology convergence	Literature review	Identified research prospects in the areas of decentralized computing for AI.	Distributed-ledger-based AI applications.	Germany
Gill et al. [33] explored the transformative effects of BC,	IoT + AI + BC	Cloud Computing	Literature review	Proposed a conceptual model for cloud	Quality of Service (QoS) model in	UK, India, China, Canada,

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Table 2 (continued)

Author(s), year, and contributions	Technology convergence	Explored areas	Methodology employed	Context	Business model	Countries
IoT, and AI on cloud computing.				futurology to explore the influence of emerging paradigms and technologies.	cloud computing systems.	Australia, Nigeria, Turkey, Iran, and USA
Keršič et al. [44] presented a blockchain-and AI-based platform for global employability.	AI + BC	Matchmaking process	Literature review	Offered adequate project matching and recruitment process in organizations.	AI-BC architectural model.	Slovenia
Markopoulos et al. [58] investigated the use of AI and BC for human resources.	AI + BC	Team management	Literature review	Suggested a teaming requirements elicitation process.	AI and BC for Knowledge management.	UK and Finland
Phansalkar et al. [66] explored the decentralizing of AI applications with BC.	AI + BC	AI applications	Literature review	Presented strategies for addressing challenges faced in amalgamating AI and BC to create greater value.	Decentralized AI models.	India
Salah et al. [70] presented a review on BC applications for AI.	AI + BC	BC for AI	Literature review	Identified and examined open research issues of utilizing BC for AI.	AI based BC and IoT-enabled ecosystems	UAE, Pakistan, and USA
Daniels et al. [27] discussed on the application of IoT, AI, and BC.	IoT + AI + BC	Technology convergence	Literature review	Aimed to achieve proper oversight to achieving a secure platform and architecture for IoT, AI, and BC .	AI, BC, and IoT supply chain solution.	USA
Dinh and Thai [30] studied the integration of AI and BC in the society.	AI + BC	Society	Literature review	Summarized existing efforts and discussed the potential of AI and BC.	Smart, decentralized, and secure solution.	USA
Xing and Marwala [87] researched on the synergy of AI and BC.	AI + BC	Business	Literature review	Suggested deploying AI to deliver bug-free smart contract to achieve blockchain 2.0.	BC based AI solutions.	South Africa

the use of AI across industries could provide an additional global economic gain of about USD 13 trillion by the end of 2030 [70].

A report by the World Economic Forum forecasted that by 2025, about 10 % of the world's Gross domestic product (GDP) may be stored on a DLT [65]. The convergence of AI and IoT (as AIoT), and DLT can help to develop innovative services, products, and platforms. Accordingly, both AI and DLT can be integrated with IoT to design robust and secure mobility services. The infusion of IoT and AI as AIoT enables physical devices employed in cities to autonomously function and subsequently providing intelligent mobility services. AIoT and DLT can decrease variable costs, promotes transparency, and increases service reliability for citizens in smart cities. The convergence of these disruptive technologies holds the promise of achieving valuable and useful use cases for a smarter, safer, secure, and more sustainable city. Therefore, this study discusses the convergence of AIoT, and DLT to provide use cases for promoting intelligent mobility services in smart cities. These technologies have potential to improve sustainable urban digitalization towards the actualization of smart cities. AI helps to understand and analyze data produced from IoT which is stored in a centralized architecture which is not secure. In contrast DLT provides a decentralized data storage and can enhance the security of AI system.

Converging AIoT and DLT can create value added services that could provide totally new or improve services [29]. The deployment of both AIoT and DLT can complement each other to overcome the limitations of each other. For example, DLT can improve transparency, trustworthiness, and explainable or interpretability for AIoT systems, which are often characterized as black box [42,51]. DLT can offer trust, explainability, and improve privacy for AIoT-based systems, while AIoT can enhance scalability while resolving personalization and governance issues faced in DLT [51]. The technological convergence of AI, IoT, and DLT can be remarkably promising for data management towards the automatization of city's mobility services. However, there are fewer scientifically sound and systematic approaches proposed to support the common understanding for cities on how the convergence of AI, IoT, and DLT might be deployed together to support current mobility or public transportation processes and how the capabilities of these technologies may support each other.

4.5. TOE framework for convergence of AIoT and DLT in smart cities

Over the years several theories, frameworks, and models such as the diffusion of innovation, technology acceptance model, task technology fit, and others that have been employed to examine the adoption of disruptive technologies in smart cities. Nonetheless, most of these theories or models are more appropriate for exploring technology acceptance and do not extensively consider the environmental or organizational aspects mostly in smart cities [69]. Conversely, the Technology Organization Environment (TOE) framework is one of the approaches that offers a more holistic variables that is well suited for examining challenges faced in urban

Fig. 8. Synergic benefits of AIoT and DLT.

context. As such the TOE framework have been employed to offer a theoretical perspective for examining smart city development [28, 57,63,69,81,86].

The TOE framework was proposed by Tornatzky et al., [77], and has been employed in ICT based research to successfully predict institutional adoption of innovations [17]. As the technological convergence of AIoT and DLT poses several challenges. This study examines the factors that influences the convergence of AIoT and DLT in smart cities grounded on the TOE framework. The TOE framework is conceptualized based on three main variables which comprises of the environmental, technological, and organizational context.

- The technological variable involves the technology characteristics such as the complexity, accessibility, perceived benefits, and data security ([28,57,81]; Anthony [40]).
- Secondly the organizational variable refers to the resources and the characteristics of the institution as related to the size of the corporation, financial resources, skill level of employees and managerial structure [63,69,86].
- The environmental which is the third variable includes the conditions outside the institution which may range from the regulatory environment or macroeconomic context, and the institution's competitors [69,86].

This study opted to employ the TOE framework as it considers the fact that the acceptance and use of innovative technology is often multi-dimensional encompassing diverse factors that need to be assessed. Moreover, the TOE framework was proposed to examine institutional level adoption of various technological services and products as well as digital innovation, which is in line with the study area of technological convergence of AIoT and DLT in smart cities. Finally, As pointed out by Baker [21]; Rjab et al. [69] the TOE is characterized by its ability to incorporate new attributes without conflict, thereby providing facilitating the flexibility needed to examine the adoption of disruptive technologies in different contexts.

4.5.1. Factors that impact the convergence of AIoT and DLT in smart cities

The main factors that impact the convergence of AIoT and DLT in smart cities as shown in Fig. 9 based on the TOE framework.

In smart cities the *technological* context includes all of the technologies that are important for the digitalization of the cities to become smarter. This entails legacy technologies that are already in use and emerging technologies available but not currently in use [21]. The current state of city's existing technologies is paramount in influencing the adoption process of AIoT and DLT in smart cities as citizens knowledge and of these technologies set an extensive limit on the pace and scope of technological change that a city can deploy. The first challenge in achieving technology convergence of AIoT and DLT in smart cities will be based on how to ensure that the

needed infrastructure is made available. As each individual technologies AI, IoT, and DLT will need to be *self-efficient*. Presently, this is especially an issue with DLT such as blockchain which is faced with *scaling* challenges [56]. Accordingly, the inherent infrastructure deployed by AIoT and DLT needs to be efficient by supporting hi-speed connectivity. However, the ability to maintain the *efficiency and scalability* of the entire system across a distributed networked system is still an open challenge [60].

Another challenge is the limited *performance* overhead which exists with decentralized federated AI, which is more common in contract to traditional ML models [22]. In providing intelligent mobility services to citizens in smart cities based on the convergent of AIoT and DLT can provide real time information on the public transport services available to demand, recommend alternate routes to commuters in real time, change traffic lights to optimize traffic flow, etc. However, the collected data from citizens can significantly result to *data privacy and ethical concerns* as citizens movement and location can potentially be tracked and also recorded [56]. Likewise, IoT devices such as sensors and metering devices can continuously collect citizens' personal data which is stored in the ledgers if public DLT is used [70]. Hence, it is encouraged to deploy private DLTs which enables that the *data privacy* is re-enforced by enabling encryption for controlling data access within the distributed ledgers. However, as stated by Salah et al. [70] such private DLT systems will restrict access to data necessary for ML algorithms to processing and preform correct and accurate analytics and decision-making support.

Additionally, DLT enable authentic and secure data processing, however, in public DLT based platforms the collected data may be publicly available and accessible for all users. This can be a privacy concern for citizens uptake of DLT based applications if public based DLTs are deployed in smart cities [70]. Besides, with the collection of personal data stored in distributed ledger, privacy has become another critical problem. As pointed out by Sun Yin et al. [75] most DLT such as blockchain systems often require smart contracts to generate metadata, which can be used to reveal some personal information of citizens, even when the data is encrypted. Thus, *data anonymity or privacy and security* is needed in decentralized AI based system to avoid poisoned data attacks in ML models. However, redesigning or modifying the complex ML algorithms for enhanced privacy and security of distributed data is challenging. Likewise, it is difficult to achieve enhance data privacy and security without simply interfering with the performance and throughput of the intelligent system.

Evidence from the literature [56] argued that large-scale convergent systems are mostly faced with *security and risks* challenges. Thus, designers of AIoT and DLT platforms will need to adequate address ethical use of data and also re-enforce cyber security for AI, IoT, and DLT individually which is more difficult to achieve as the smart city ecosystem becomes larger [56]. Also, there is need to ensure adequate data privacy in providing digital services in smart cities while supporting legitimate use of data for the common good of the citizens [56]. Furthermore, the *organizational context* involves the city's' internal structures and processes that may inhibit or foster the adoption of the adoption process of AIoT and DLT in smart cities (Anthony [15,40]). More broadly, findings from the literature suggested that the institutional structure influences the innovation adoption process [21]. In the context of this study the organizational factors large-scale use cases in smart cities such as intelligent mobility services depend on the appropriate *availability* of infrastructure to all stakeholders in the urban environment.

Fig. 9. TOE factors that impact the convergence of AIoT and DLT in smart cities.

This will necessitate the *provision of funding* from the government including research and development efforts, with forward-looking and well-timed infrastructure planning [56]. Additionally, from the *governance perspective* consider the *management and control* of millions (if not billions) of heterogeneous IoT devices deployed in smart cities is a challenge for *monitoring* and creating interface that enables the devices to seamlessly communicate and securely transact autonomously [14,56]. The governance of a DLT platform among different stakeholders and participants is a tedious task. This is also a challenge in consortium or private DLT [20]. As several issues arise when governing the operation of DLT such as which type of DLT to deploy, who troubleshoots and administers the distributed ledger, the deployment location of the network nodes, who programs the smart contracts, settlement any potential dispute, choice of trusted oracles, procedures for executing off-chain activities, execution of side channels, complying with regulations and standards, and many others [70].

Moreover, the use of DLT in smart cities is faced with a number of *risks and liabilities* as well. This includes the open, often permissionless, decentralized, transparent nature of DLT which can raise a number of *complex legal and regulatory issues* [56]. These includes among other how adhere to the personal data protection requirements of GDPR to address issues related to the legally binding status of transactions and data carried out in the distributed ledger. This also involves issues of specifying which laws are applicable in cross jurisdictional systems, to unclear policies related to the liability and legality around actions executed by AIoT and DLT-based smart contracts [11,56]. This is evident when ML algorithms as autonomous systems collect, processes and evaluate data to take actions based on at their own discretion. In case of any issues who is held *liable* for these actions [12]. In smart cities there are also governance issues related to liability as related to AIoT-based decision making. This is linked to explainable AI which is needed to ensure that citizens can know how a machine makes a particular decision [56].

For instance, considering the development of *non-repudiation* in the decision-making processes of AI and the application of ML model within time sequenced public ledgers [22]. In addition, in smart cities the *environmental context* includes the structure of the city, the presence or absence of service providers of digital or data driven services for the citizens a well as the regulatory landscape [21,52], that regulates the provision and use of these digital services provided to citizens and other stakeholder in the urban environment. This is because government regulations and policies can either be beneficial or detrimental to disruptive technologies such as AI and DLT based innovation (Anthony [40]). The environmental factors as related to convergence of AIoT and DLT in smart cities include *regulatory and legal barriers* that will need to be addressed, for example polices around *data protection legislation* such as the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) or legality related use of cryptocurrency for payment of transactions [56]. Another key challenge is linked to achieving *interoperability* across different technologies [8,24].

Formally achieving a standardization for open platforms will help to achieve a reliable, secure, and resilient applications. Presently, there is a lack of technical specifications and models to enable *integration and interoperability* of DLTs with other external systems [41]. The convergence of AIoT and DLT in smart cities will require interoperability between large-scale urban systems. For example, to achieve an intelligent mobility service driven by AIoT and DLT, these platforms must be standardized to talk to each other. DLTs have many intriguing security properties. However, they also present some drawbacks. For example, public blockchains introduce transaction costs and delays that are often intolerable in many IoT use cases. Moreover, other drawbacks that may negatively impact the convergence of AIoT and DLT includes the lack of *governance, standards, interoperability, and regulations* associated with AIoT and especially DLT. Although there is ongoing work by IEEE, W3C, NIST, ISO/TC, ITU, and a few standards bodies as highlighted in the literature [41], to improve the governance, standardization, integration, and interoperability of DLT and this will in turn improve the convergence of AIoT and DLT [70].

This will require contribution not only from technologists, but also policy makers and standardization bodies as well [56]. Furthermore, *standardization* across AIoT and DLT will also improve explainability, transparency, and visibility of ML models which will accelerate the update of AIoT and DLT in different domains [60]. Moreover, at national and international level, institutional and governmental policies, guidelines, rules, regulations, and laws is needed to be put in place for AI and DLT deployment especially for public DLT transactions involving automated payments and funding using cryptocurrencies. According to Salah et al. [70] these regulations are to be directed at formulating models and proof of concepts that can contribute to specifying the right set of technical standards and interoperability for converging AIoT and DLT services as well as architectural model deployment [70]. Lastly, another challenge involves how to improve the *level of trust* faced by individuals who participates in the distributed network when financial and non-financial data are shared [22].

4.6. Findings on use cases

4.6.1. Use case for a decentralized intelligent electric carpooling

Synchronized AIoT and DLT can integrating data from multiple sources to improve interoperability and connectivity between different transport systems deployed in smart cities such as traffic management system, rapid transit systems, urban rail systems, etc., [50]. A use case for an intelligent mobility service in smart cities can comprises of an electric car sharing scheme as described in the literature (Jnr, 2024), which can be facilitated by the convergence of AIoT and DLT. In this use case IoT devices such as cameras, sensors and smart meters are installed in the electric car provided by a mobility service provider to facilitate citizens mobility. The electric car is deployed in the urban environment as an intelligent IoT device connected to the internet as well as the DLT network. DLT can support the deployment of a distributed and decentralized marketplaces and management platform [72], for electric car sharing in smart cities without the need for any middleman or centralized authority to govern the entire system [13,19]. Citizens can book and use the electric cars for a specific period based on the carpooling business model operated by the mobility service provider [8,18]. The electric car can be used from one location to another as seen in Fig. 10. The use of the electric carpooling is based on the distance or time driven and DLT is employed facilitated by smart contracts to enable secure micropayments without the need for any intermediary

[43].

DLT ensures that payment can be made directly to the electric car using digital wallet installed in the car and also in the mobile application of the citizens handheld device via Bluetooth communication which is used to open the electric car after payment has been made in cryptocurrency or in local currency. Accordingly, a pay-per-use payment business model could be implemented [71]. Using the digital wallet DLT can not only receive payments but potentially make payment for a number of transport related systems, including toll payment, road user charges, etc. [43]. The digital wallet of the electric car is linked to the private bank account of the mobility service provider. Additionally, all available electric cars are connected to the DLT network and data such as the performance, usage, and downtime is collected and stored within the decentralized and distributed ledger or database. AI could leverage these collected data to optimize the management and maintenance of the electric car fleets. For example, the data can be used to suggest time and date for regular maintenance of electric cars that are frequently used as well as support to quickly dispatch maintenance staff in case of an unseen fault. Additionally, utilizing real time data AIoT and DLT can help to carry out and automate maintenance tasks including planning and scheduling preventive maintenance. AI can provide self-optimizing charging systems based on the current energy market price to recommend time of the day suitable for charging EV fleets based on ML algorithms [56]. Finally, AI can make predictive maintenance by precisely suggesting electric car parts such as the battery that may need replacement [71].

4.6.2. Use case for decentralized intelligent ride-sharing

Another use case involves deploying AIoT and DLT to enable ride-sharing where DLT can allow secure payments between different parties enabling drivers and passengers to share an electric car based on an agreed time, date, and start and end location booked (Jnr, 2024). This supports a direct transaction between the passengers and the drivers (and possible driverless cars in future) [43]. Using DLT will offer the prospective for reduce ride costs as the driver or mobility service provider gets majority of the fee with small charge being charged as transaction fee for DLT. This supports an opens and democratic ride-sharing business model for smart cities thereby decreasing monopolized ride-sharing [8]. DLT provides the ability for mobility service providers to have time stamped tamperproof records of mobility related data storage. Also, DLT supports micro-payments process using smart contract without any charges. DLT further helps to freely manage the ownership, identity, and credentials of users that book electric cars. The convergence of AIoT and DLT can facilitate a range of innovative options for decentralized intelligent ride sharing as seen in Fig. 11.

Likewise, DLT could help to save real-time location information collected from IoT devices installed in EVs. IoT devices such as sensors can be employed for people counters and/or DLT based online payment systems for electric carpooling. The online payment can also enable micro-payments for citizens who rent and use the electric cars, as well as other multimodal mobility means. Provision of real-time mobility traffic update from data produced from IoT devices deployed in the public transport infrastructure. This real-time data could be employed by ML algorithms to manage the entire Electric Vehicle (EV) fleet in real-time to assist mobility service providers in planning improvements, changes, and possible expansion of mobility service [56]. IoT sensors can be installed in parking lots to enable autonomous parking and charging system based on real-time collected by IoT devices and analyzed by AI to deliver information on available charging and parking spots for electric cars [8]. Furthermore, the collected data from IoT devices can be combined with the current traffic patterns in the city to manage the increased demand for parking by providing information to citizens on the free place to park at a given time, day, and location [56].

Fig. 10. AIoT and DLT for decentralized intelligent electric carpooling.

Fig. 11. AIoT and DLT for decentralized intelligent ride sharing.

5. Discussions and implications

5.1. Discussions

The massive generation and production of data by sensing systems, social media, IoT devices, and digital platforms in smart cities have contributed to the emergence of AI which is a sub area of computer science which aims to simulate, extend, and expand human intelligence. Evidence from the McKinsey Global Institute projected that AI market will grow to 13 trillion dollars by the year 2030 [83]. Although AI, IoT, and DLT based solutions have been proposed to promote the sustainable development of cities for secure, efficient, and intelligent systems in urban context, they are still in their infancy [75]. Accordingly, this study explores the technological convergence of disruptive technologies such as AI and IoT as AIoT and DLT highlighting the potential of these technologies for intelligent mobility services in smart cities. Findings from this study presents the role of AI, IoT, and DLT for intelligent mobility services in smart cities, technology convergence of IoT and DLT in smart cities, and significance of AIoT-based DLT for intelligent mobility services in smart cities. More importantly this study adopted the technology organization environment framework as a baseline to investigate the factors that impact the convergence of AIoT and DLT in smart cities. Besides, findings of a use case for a decentralized intelligent electric car sharing and use case for decentralized intelligent ride-sharing was presented to highlight how AIoT and DLT can contribute to provide innovative mobility services to citizens in smart cities.

DLT offers a peer-to-peer decentralized and distributed system that guarantees tamper-proofing via the underlying time stamp technology and hash algorithm using some cryptographic algorithms [83]. The integration of AIoT and DLT can lead to mutual reinforcement towards the development of a decentralized data driven ecosystem for distributed data storage and management, and governance of urban infrastructure and platforms in smart cities. To improve public transportation the integration of AIoT and DLT can create predictive system that can contribute to improve to traffic flow within the city. Using these AIoT and DLT, citizens can own and control their mobility related data. DLT can provide citizens with a digital identity that ensures data sovereignty and traceable in real time, thereby restoring trust in the digital ecosystem by presenting greater transparency. DLT reinforces data authentication and authorization for user account management. Thus, enabling citizens to access mobility related data in real-time. For mobility service providers DLT enable a scalable infrastructural solution with reduced variable maintenance costs. Additionally, the convergence of AIoT and DLT can improve current business practices in smart cities by introducing new business use cases for greater agility, flexibility, and cost-effective data sharing and digitalization of urban processes.

5.2. Practical implications

This study is one of the first articles that attempt to investigate the integration of disruptive technologies to improve urban services. Therefore, this study aims to examine the convergence of AIoT and DLT to support secure, decentralized intelligent mobility services in smart cities and as such offers practical implications. The deployment of DLT supports mainly back-end processes, while AIoT mostly supports front end activities providing a user interface for citizens to interact with in managing their mobility related services. The technological convergence of these technologies can offer value added services via the seamless integration of AI based automated processing connected to the decentralized information sharing powered by DLT. While IoT employs a standardized communication

protocol with AI-systems as AIoT which then enables interface communication with DLT. This reduces complexity and limits overall system maintenance [29]. Evidence from this study also provides practical implications to different stakeholders, including AIoT and DLT developers, IoT vendors, practitioners, researchers, and mobility service providers. For mobility service providers, this study provides knowledge on the potential of integrating AIoT and DLT to improve business performance in creating new mobility business models that enables a resilient electric carpooling and intelligent ride sharing.

The findings provide use cases on how AIoT and DLT can improve existing mobility sharing economy. This study also provides insights to AIoT and DLT developers on how to integrate these disruptive technologies to achieve business synergy. The knowledge gotten from the study can help AIoT and DLT developers on how they can collaborate to develop intelligent and decentralized platforms that offer better sovereignty, governance, performance, and better security for user privacy and data confidentiality. The findings also provide recommendations on the potential of AIoT and DLT for IoT vendors to better identify possible market for AIoT and DLT based urban solutions in smart cities. Finally, this study advances the knowledge of practitioners and researchers by providing a road map to integrate AIoT and DLT to provide new services or enrich existing services in smart cities. Thus, this study empowers both practitioners and researchers with evidence on the opportunities to be derived from the convergence of AIoT and DLT to enhance the resilience, development, and robustness data driven services in smart cities. The integration of AIoT and DLT can create immutable, secure, decentralized mobility sharing system for the citizens and mobility service provider. Besides, evidence from this study suggest that the convergence of AIoT and DLT enables intelligent service automation and higher efficiency leading to less manual processes in smart cities.

5.3. Research implications

Leveraging of AIoT and decentralized technology such as DLT has the potential to transform smart cities services but provided intelligent mobility services. In this research, the TOE framework was adopted to examine the technological, organizational, and environmental factors that impacts the convergence of AIoT and DLT in smart cities. Findings from this study aims to investigate the current state of research, main challenges, and future research directions concerning the convergence of AIoT and DLT. Moreover, findings from this study point out the strengths and limitations related to deployment of AIoT and DLT in smart cities. This study makes several noteworthy contributions. First, this study sheds light on the applicability of AIoT and DLT integration specifically for intelligent mobility services, which to date, remains limited, wherein such understandings are arguably important given that public transportation is important to the economy, and thus, the transformation to intelligent mobility services is relevant for digitalization of cities into smarter cities.

Additionally, this article elucidates the potential benefits emerging technologies can offer to enhance mobility service providers. By integrating AIoT and DLT, decentralized intelligent platforms and algorithms can be developed to facilitate a citizen-driven mobility sharing services which gives absolute sovereignty to the citizens to take control over their data. Employing DLT will also provide a provenance-based audit trail for mobility service providers to access the permission on citizens-centric data to build trusted and open ML models that runs data analytics without revealing personally identifiable information [38]. Implication from this study addresses the integration of AIoT and DLT, which is becoming a necessary solution in smart cities that enables intelligent, decentralized, and secure sharing of data as well as the seamless operation of networking and communications systems [75]. Overall, this article offers insights for practitioners and researchers interested in getting knowledge on the interdisciplinary applications of AI, IoT, and DLT in urban context. By providing these insights evidence from this study contributes to the sustainable development of urban innovations.

6. Conclusion

AI, IoT, and DLT are one of the hallmark technologies in smart cities. Although these technologies are quite different in their own capabilities, the subject of convergence has received attention among researchers and practitioners alike. Nevertheless, there are fewer studies that examined the applications of AI and IoT as AIoT and DLT in smart city domain. Grounded on the TOE framework findings from this article presents current research status and possible opportunities on the convergence of AIoT and DLT. Accordingly, this study carried out a systematic literature review to examine the current state-of-the-art on the technological convergence of AIoT and DLT in smart cities, identifies the technological, organizational, and environmental factors that impacts the convergence of AIoT and DLT in smart cities, and lastly presents use cases of how the convergence of AIoT and DLT support the actualization of intelligent mobility services in smart cities. Findings from this study also describes how DLT can advance AIoT applications, as well as how AIoT can advance DLT systems. The integration of AIoT and DLT can enable a personalized and immutable registration of citizens, while anonymously protecting their data to enable a more citizen-centered mobility. Findings from this study suggest that AIoT and DLT can be drivers for sustainable development of intelligent mobility applications and services for instance intelligent transport and traffic systems, intelligent electric carpooling, mobility as a service, intelligent ride sharing which in turn can improve the future of public transportation in smart cities. Furthermore, future research will be dedicated to collect primary data to further evaluate the integration of AIoT and DLT in smart cities. Qualitative data will be collected to evaluate the deployment of AIoT and DLT to provide value added services to citizens and other stakeholders in smart cities environment. Lastly, AI techniques such as FL can be deployed as a potential solution, as there is a lack of FL-based AIoT solutions for intelligent mobility services in smart cities.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Bokolo Anthony Jnr: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Methodology, Investigation,

Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Supplementary materials

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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